

Fabrication and characterizations of PCDTBT : PC₇₁BM bulk heterojunction solar cells using air brush coating method

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Abstract : Organic solar cells have attracted a significant amount of attention due to the need to develop an inexpensive clean and sustainable renewable energy source. We report on the fabrication of poly [*N*-9''-hepta-decanyl-2,7-carbazole-alt-5,5-(4',7'-di-2-thienyl-2',1',3'-benzothiadiazole)]/[6,6]-phenyl-C71-butyric acid methyl ester blend active layer using airbrush spray coating method in mixed solvents. The surface morphology of the active layers deposited with different parameters was examined using Atomic Force Microscopy. The current density-voltage (*J*-*V*) characteristics of photovoltaic cells were measured under the illumination of simulated solar light with 100 mW/cm² (AM 1.5G) by an Oriel 1000 W solar simulator. The power conversion efficiency of the solar cell is more than 5%.

Keywords : Organic solar cell, spray coating, AFM, PCBM.

Introduction

Organic solar cells have attracted a significant amount of attention due to the need to develop an inexpensive clean and sustainable renewable energy source. During the past decade, there have been intensive researches on cost-effective organic solar cells based on conjugated polymers^{1,2}. The discovery of an ultra fast and efficient photo-induced electron transfer between a *p*-conjugated polymer and fullerene boosted the development of solution processed polymer-based solar cells as a cheap alternative to Si-based ones^{3,4}. Polymer-based bulk heterojunction solar cells have now achieved power conversion efficiencies of >8% closing in on the 10% efficiency milestone⁵. Significant efforts have been made over the past few years to develop new efficient electron donor polymers. In particular, low-band gap polymers are required for an optimized overlapping of the absorption spectrum with the solar emission spectrum^{6,7}. Bulk-heterojunction solar cells are complicated systems derived partially from the need to use donor-acceptor combinations to facilitate charge generation. Bulk heterojunction films consist of a blend of donor and acceptor materials with (ideally) interconnected phase-separated domains.

Spin-coating is the general fabrication method in the research field of OPV's. The spin-coating method has been widely used in laboratories, due to its high precision and reproducibility. However, there is inherently a large amount of waste materials in spin-coating and it is not compatible with roll-to-roll or large area manufacturing. Air brush spray methods are inexpensive and allow high throughput however precise deposition control is limited¹³. In this paper, we report the effect of processing conditions on the performance of PCDTBT : PC₇₁BM based cells, and the nano-scale morphology of active layers using spray coating technique in mixed solvents : chloroform (CF) and 1,2-dichlorobenzene (*o*-DCB). These solvents were chosen primarily due to the good solubility of PCDTBT and PC₇₁BM in them. The parameters such as spraying time and substrate-nozzle distance were varied and the coated active layers of PCDTBT : PC₇₁BM were investigated.

Results and discussion

Morphology study of PCDTBT : PC₇₁BM blends :

The AFM topographic images of the PCDTBT : PC₇₁BM blends with different blend ratios : 1 : 1 (b); 1 : 2 (c); 1 : 3 (d); 1 : 4 (e) are shown in Fig. 1. These

composition ratios are equal to the weight ratios that is composition are 50, 67, 75 and 80 wt% PC₇₁BM in PCDTBT correspondingly. It is indicated that peak to valley values are 4.83, 5.01, 13.29, 7.03 and rms roughness are 0.74, 0.92, 1.54, 1.06 nm respectively. The highest peak to valley and roughness values were obtained by PCDTBT : PC₇₁BM blend with 75 wt% PC₇₁BM content. At lower PC₇₁BM loadings, PCDTBT : PC₇₁BM blends display such high miscibility that homogeneous films are obtained with smoother surfaces than the pristine PCDTBT film itself. On further increasing the PC₇₁BM loading, a large number of granular PC₇₁BM aggregates from with a size distribution between 50 and 100 nm, uniformly dispersed in the PCDTBT matrix. For the ratios of 1 : 3 and 1 : 4, the surfaces of the blend films become increasingly uneven and large PCBM aggregations are observed with a similar size distribution of 100–300 nm. The images were recorded on a film area of 2000 × 2000 nm.

Photovoltaic performance of PCDTBT : PC₇₁BM OPV's :

The PV parameters were extracted from the current density-voltage (*J-V*) curves under AM 1.5G illumination condition (100 mW cm⁻²), at room temperature. A small reduction in open circuit voltage (*V*_{oc}) was observed with the increase of PC₇₁BM concentration. This trend was previously observed in other polymer : fullerene system devices. The exact reason for the reduction in *V*_{oc} is not clear and its value of around 0.9 V is well correlated to the difference between the LUMO level of PC₇₁BM and the HOMO level of PCDTBT⁵. The highest *J*_{sc} and PCE are obtained at the ratio 1 : 3 and reduced at the ratio 1 : 4 of PCDTBT : PC₇₁BM which can be explained by the fact that, with increasing PC₇₁BM loading, a large number of PC₇₁BM clusture with size above 100 nm dispersed in the film not only reduce the PCDTBT : PC₇₁BM interface but also act as charge traps resulting in a strong deterioration of photovoltaic performance.

Fig. 1. AFM images (2 μm × 2 μm) of pristine PCDTBT film and PCDTBT : PC₇₁BM blend films spray-coated from mixed solvents. The blend ratios are indicated in the images.

Table 1. Performance parameters of BHJ solar cells based on PCDTBT : PC₇₁BM composite with different weight ratios under AM 1.5G illumination of 100 mW cm⁻²

PCDTBT : PC ₇₁ BM weight ratio	Active layer (nm)	V _{oc} (V)	J _{sc} (mA cm ⁻²)	FF	PCE (%)
1 : 1	122	0.93 ± 0.2	5.39 ± 0.1	58.09 ± 0.3	2.9 ± 0.1
1 : 2	120	0.91 ± 0.1	7.14 ± 0.2	60.02 ± 0.1	3.9 ± 0.1
1 : 3	117	0.89 ± 0.1	10.18 ± 0.4	64.03 ± 0.4	5.8 ± 0.2
1 : 4	94	0.88 ± 0.2	8.29 ± 0.1	63.07 ± 0.3	4.6 ± 0.1

Fig. 2. (i) Molecular structures of (a) donor, (b) acceptor and (c) hole transport layer, (ii) relative energy level diagram and (iii) ITO/PEDOT : PSS/PCDTBT : PC₇₁BM/Al structure.

Experimental

Materials, device fabrication, testing and film characterization :

PCDTBT and PC₇₁BM were purchased from 1-material. These chemicals act as an electron donor (*D*) and acceptor (*A*) materials, respectively. PCDTBT was purified twice with chloroform and PC₇₁BM was used as received. Pre-patterned indium tin oxide (ITO)-coated glass with a sheet resistance of 12 Ω/□ were cleaned with detergent, ultrasonicated in acetone and isopropyl alcohol for 15 min and dried in an oven at 120 °C. UV-ozone treatment was then performed for 15 min. A film of PEDOT : PSS was spin cast (5000 rpm for 40 s) on top of the ITO substrates and was dried for 15 min at 140 °C. The active layer solutions were prepared by mixing the polymer and PC₇₁BM in different blend ratios of 1 : 1; 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 were dissolved in *o*-DCB and CF (3 : 1 ratio) with 3% DIO. By introducing the nitrogen gas with the pressure of 8.5 × 10⁴ Pa into the spray apparatus the solution of PCDTBT : PC₇₁BM were spray cast onto the PEDOT : PSS film to form the active layer. More than 70 devices cast in different PCDTBT : PC₇₁BM ratios and were characterized. The design of the solar cell device was in the form of a sandwich structure of the photoactive polymeric layer between an anode electrode

of indium tin oxide (ITO) and a metal cathode of aluminium (Al). The molecular structure, relative energy level diagram and device construction of ITO/PEDOT : PSS/PCDTBT : PC₇₁BM/Al were illustrated in the Fig. 2. The surface morphology of the blend layers were examined by atomic force microscopy (AFM) using a Seiko Instruments SPA400-SPI4000. All AFM images were taken in dynamic force mode at optimal force. The current-voltage characteristics of the fabricated solar cells were measured by employing the Advantest-R-6441A.C. meter and a 100 mW solar simulator with an air mass 1.5G (AM 1.5G) filter.

Conclusion

In summary, the spray coating technology, has identified several important parameters such as nozzle-substrate distance, choice of solvent mixture of co-solvent and the additive that influence the morphology optimization. Using these parameters in this work, we have explored the possibility of fabricating solar cell devices by a hand-held airbrush with an active layer composed of PCDTBT and PC₇₁BM. CF and *o*-DCB were shown to be an appropriate carrier solvent with 3% DIO and we obtain a promising PCE 5.8% on average without any special treatment under room temperature condition. These indicate that

the spray-coating method can replace the conventional spin-coating and can be applied to the roll-to-roll process as well as the large-area fabrication.

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